

Sashi (CN842-15-5, IET14105), a high-yielding, long-slender grain variety for shallow water conditions in West Bengal, India

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Most varieties cultivated for shallow water conditions have bold grains, resulting in a low return from low market value. A breeding program began in 1984-85 to select for long-slender grain lines only from segregating generations along with other desired characters such as high grain yield and disease and pest resistance.

Sashi, derived from crossing IR50 and Patnai 23, was first nominated to the All-India testing under the Initial Variety Trial (shallow water) with IET14105 in 1993 after testing at the RRS under shallow water conditions. Based on overall performance, it was promoted to the Advanced Variety Trial (shallow water) in 1995 and subsequently recommended for cultivation in West Bengal and eastern Uttar Pradesh in 1997, released for West Bengal by the state Variety Release Committee in 1999 for shallow water areas, and finally approved for seed production by the Variety Identification Committee in 2000.

Before its release, IET14105 (CN842-15-5) was tested extensively under the Front Line Demonstration Program trial in different districts of West Bengal in the 1998 and 1999 kharif (wet) season in farmers' fields. Results (Table 1) unequivocally proved the superiority of the variety over other checks with improved grain type (Table 2). The variety has now gained popularity for its long-slender grains; higher yield;

Table 1. Performance of IET14105 (Sashi) under the Front Line Demonstration Program in different districts of West Bengal, 1998 kharif.

Variety	Farmers (no.)	Area (ha)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Mean grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	% increase
<i>1998 kharif</i>					
24-Parganas (South)					
IET14105	38	15	3.6–5.4	4.5	–
Salibahan	38	5	2.5–3.4	3.0	53 over Salibahan
Patnai 23	38	–	–	2.2	101 over Patnai
Hooghly					
IET14105	24	10	3.5–4.5	4.0	–
Bipasa	24	10	3.3–4.5	3.9	3 over Bipasa
Swarna	24	–	–	3.8	4 over Swarna
Midnapur (West)					
IET14105	31	10	3.0–5.0	4.0	–
Bipasa	31	10	2.5–5.5	4.0	7 over Bipasa
Swarna	31	–	–	3.7	8 over Swarna
<i>1999 kharif</i>					
24-Parganas (North)					
IET14105	47	12	5.0–5.2	5.0	–
IET5656	47	8	3.8–3.9	3.9	28
Burdwan					
IET14105	9	10	3.8–4.5	4.1	–
Swarna	9	10	3.0–3.7	3.5	17
Malda					
IET14105	4	5	–	4.2	–
Swarna	4	5	–	4.0	5
Hooghly					
IET14105	13	10	3.5–4.5	4.1	–
IET5656	13	10	3.0–4.1	3.9	5
24-Parganas (South)					
IET14105	30	10	3.2–3.8	3.5	–
Local varieties	30	10	1.9–2.4	2.0	75
Murshidabad					
IET14105	8	10	2.7–5.8	4.9	–
IET5656	8	10	2.6–4.5	4.3	12

tolerance for submergence; better straw height suitable for animal feed and domestic use in urban areas; tolerance for diseases and pests, particularly sheath blight and sheath rot, which mainly prevail in shallow-water ecosystems;

and tolerance for lodging. Based on this, IET14105 was released as Sashi in West Bengal in 1999 and subsequently elevated for breeder seed production in 2000.

Table 2. Comparative data on grain and quality characteristics of some lowland cultivars.

Characteristic	Sashi	Salibahan	Pronava	Swarna	Swarnadhan	Mahsuri	Pankaj
Milling recovery (%)	70.0	67.8	69.5	69.8	–	75.8	73.4
Head rice recovery (%)	65.0	64.9	67.0	66.0	–	59.2	58.8
Kernel length (mm)	6.47	5.27	5.81	5.32	5.6	5.42	6.04
Kernel breadth (mm)	1.96	2.22	2.27	2.14	2.4	2.63	2.42
Length/breadth	3.30	2.37	2.37	2.48	2.3	2.65	2.34
Grain type	Long slender	Short bold	Short bold	Short bold	Long bold	Medium slender	Long bold
Grain chalkiness	Very occasional	Occasional	Occasional	Occasional	–	–	–
Alkali value	6.6	5.7	5.8	–	–	–	–

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